

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.2523 Max: 63.4162	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1308 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1381-1383	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:	
DEFINITION northern wall of room 6 (cont. of 1217)				Covered by SU: 1280	Fills SU:	Filled by SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery	<input type="checkbox"/> Nails	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive		
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles	<input type="checkbox"/> Marble	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash			
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae	<input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones			
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia	<input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones			
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth			
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar	<input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth			
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins	<input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells			
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)				
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass						
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original	
Southern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry): 1309, 1183			
Is abutted by:			Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1280, 1209			Covers:			
Is cut by:			Cuts: (has no cut numbers yet) 1007			
Is filled by:			Fills: 1395			
OBSERVATIONS hot, dry conditions, excavated with pickaxe + trowel						
DESCRIPTION						
Position within sector: situated at the northern limit of excavation 2010, south of SU 1313 (terrace in the bedrock)						
Shape: linear, severely robbed, all of the ashlar seem to have been taken away						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):						
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):		
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight				See rev.		
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping						
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular						
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
Observations:						

SU sheet needs to be rescanned since information was added in 2011 ✓

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify) *cut into bedrock?*

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: *length: 5,80m width: 0,47 height: n.a.*

Description: *The wall seems to have been cut into the bedrock. There are two places where one might see remains of totally disintegrated ashlar. To distinguish the height of the wall it needs further excavation.*

INTERPRETATION

Northern returning wall of room 6. The wall seems to follow the alignment of wall SU1217, but is wider. The bedrock is much higher in room 6 than in the adjacent rooms and the eastern extension is also different to the other rooms (e.g. 1+3), so it could present a later addition to the building, but it is also possible that room 6 was planned to have a higher floor than the other rooms from the beginning. We are missing traces of older/different floor levels in the rooms.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *CHM*

on *04.08.2010*

Revised by *CHM*

on *04.08.2010, 20.7.2011*

PDFd by *AMS*

on *21/7/11*

Entered by

on

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<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles	<input type="checkbox"/> Marble	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash	Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
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